

A STUDY OF THE STRENGTH PROPERTIES AS DETERMINED BY THE CAO CONTENTS AND SI/AL LOW-CARBON ECO-FRIENDLY INORGANIC COMPOSITE, USING INDUSTRIAL BY PRODUCTS

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1 Introduction

Recently, as national policy called as low carbon green growth has been promoted, construction industry also tries to reduce the CO₂ emission generated when producing the cement. In other words, for the solution of environment pollution and natural resource depletion, minerals such as blast furnace slag powder, fly ash and red mud which is industrial by-product has been used. Specially, silica fume, blast furnace slag is the by-product generated when producing pig iron, so if it is recycled as admixture of concrete, it has advantages such as long term strength increases and reduction of hydrate heat, and because it is the latent hydraulic property that cannot start the hydration in the condition that has no external stimulation such as Ca(OH)₂, CaSO₄·2H₂O, alkali (Na₂O, K₂O), it also has disadvantages like congelation delay and deterioration of early strength, even though silica fume is an industrial by-product, not currently produced in Korea, obtained by collecting harmful gas dust, generated when producing ferrosilicon alloy, which is used as a deoxidizer of steel manufacture, or silicon alloy, such as silicon metal in an electric furnace; with high intensity, expression, and water tightness. However, the price is more expensive than other admixtures. Also, red-mud is generated as an industrial by-product, while aluminum hydroxide/alumina is manufactured from bauxite. Approximately 2 tons of red-mud is generated, when one ton of alumina is using the Bayer manufacturing process. In Korea, 200,000 tons of red-mud is generated every year. In domestic and foreign, a research is the red mud progressed about the recycling plan, but because recycling amount is too small compared to red mud

occurrence, it has low dyeing power compared to oxidized steel paint, and to overcome the problem that has high water-cement ratio, there are several problems used as the concrete admixture that if it is used as pozzolan material by being plasticity, its economics will be decreased, and whitening problems.

Therefore, this study has tried to produce low-carbon eco-friendly inorganic composite which can be produced at a normal temperature, with no need for high temperature plasticity, using only alkali accelerator by complementing the weak points of blast furnace slag, red-mud, and silica fume to be used as cement substitute, (not the normal concrete admixture). It has confirmed curing properties according to the additional change to the ratio and the sort of alkali solution produced by blast furnace slag, red-mud, and silica fume in the basic experiment. The study author then uses them as basic data in producing a proper mixing of low-carbon eco-friendly inorganic composites.

2 Experimental plans and methods

2.1 Basic experimental plans and methods

Experimental factors and levels were set as table 1, so as to confirm the curing properties made by the use of an alkali accelerator, and each of the industrial byproducts as the basic experiment of this study.

In order to acknowledge the influences in the types of inorganic composites, the study has set the industrial byproducts, being used as a concrete binder, into 3 levels, BFS (Blast Furnace Slag), RM (Red Mud), SF (Silica Fume), and has set the types of alkali accelerator into 5 levels; Na₂SiO₃, NaOH,

Na₂SO₄, Na₂CO₃, and K₂SiO₃.

Table 1. Basic Experiment Plan

Experiment factor		Experiment level	
Inorganic composite		Blast Furnace Slag Red Mud Silica Fume	3
Alkali accelerator		NaOH, K ₂ SiO ₃ Na ₂ CO ₃ , Na ₂ SO ₄ Na ₂ SiO ₃	5
Alkali accelerator addition	BFS ^{a)}	1, 3, 5, 7, 10 (%)	5
	RM ^{b)}	1, 3, 5, 7, 10 (%)	5
	SF ^{c)}	1, 3, 5, 7, 10 (%)	5

annotation a) BFS : Blast Furnace Slag
b) RM : Red Mud
c) SF : Silica Fume

In order to find the properties for the addition ratio of the alkali accelerator as a result of confirmation in it is curing properties, using BFS, RM and SF as inorganic composites, setting 5 levels 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10%. When using BFS, the alkali accelerator hardened in all experiments. However, when using SF, it has been hardened slowly in all experiments. When using RM it hardened only in the inorganic composites of 2 levels, NaOH and Na₂SiO₃. These results were possibly produced because potassium silicate replenished the SiO₃ due to insufficient SiO₃ in the composites of red-mud. Therefore, this study has determined to experiment with alkali accelerator, combining NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ for low-carbon inorganic composites, which have combined BFS, RM, and SF.

2.2 Planning of this experiment

This study has used alkali accelerator which has combined NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ to the BFS, RM and SF binders, based on the results of basic experiments, and has set experimental factors and levels so as to review the strength properties of the test piece specimen, according to the CaO contents and Si/Al changing rate of the inorganic binder for the experiment to develop low-carbon, eco-friendly, and

new concept inorganic composites not using cement. The mixture is demonstrated in table 3.

Table 2. Plan and Method of This Experiment

Experiment factor	Experiment level		
Inorganic composite conditions	CaO contents	20, 25, 30, 35%	4
	Si/Al ^{d)} changing rate	3, 4, 5, 6	4
Alkali accelerator	NaOH:Na ₂ SiO ₃	5 : 5	1
Curing Conditions	relative humidity (80±5)% temperature (20±2)°C		1
Experiment item	compressive strength		1

annotation d) Si/Al : SiO₂/Al₂O₃(molecular weight)

Table 3. Low-carbon Eco-friendly Inorganic composites Mix

Water (g)	Alkali accelerator (g)		Experiment level	Inorganic composite chemical component (%)		
	NaOH	Na ₂ SiO ₃		CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃
60	50	50	CaO 20%	20.5	37.1	17.9
			CaO 25%	25.0	35.3	17.1
			CaO 30%	29.6	33.5	16.3
			CaO 35%	34.9	33.0	14.7
			Si/Al 3	29.8	29.4	17.8
			Si/Al 4	29.6	33.5	16.3
			Si/Al 5	30.2	38.9	13.9
			Si/Al 6	30.2	42.1	12.7

In order to look for the strength properties, using CaO contents and the Si/Al change of BFS, RM, and SF binder, the study progressed the experiment fixing Si/Al at 4. Then the study set CaO contents at 4 levels, 20, 25, 30, and 35(%). In addition, it fixed

the CaO contents at 30%, and then set Si/Al at 4 levels, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

2.3 Methods of this experiment

Tests with an assorted mixture of low-carbon, eco-friendly inorganic composites using blast furnace slag, red-mud, and silica fume using an 18 liter mortar mixer, and implemented dry-mixing for 60 seconds at a speed of 20 rpm, after inputting BFS, RM and SF. Alkali accelerator were added, which combined NaOH and Na₂SiO₃, mixed for 120 seconds at a speed of 30, and 40 rpms, for a total of 300 seconds. After which it discharged them.

The study produced them in a 5x5x5 test mold, to measure the compressive strength of the hardened properties for each age, cured them in the low temperature (20±2°C) & humidity (80±5%) test chamber in the meantime.

Fig. 1 Low-carbon Eco-friendly Inorganic composites Mixing method

2.4 Material Used

2.4.1 Blast Furnace Slag

Density of blast furnace slag is within scope of 2.88 ~ 2.99g/cm³, and fineness can be divided into 4,000, 6,000, 8,000 cm²/g class, and the things that excesses 10µm are existed in 4,000 cm²/g class, but as getting 6,000 ~ 8,000 cm²/g, they are decreased and finer. Blast furnace slag used in this experiment has density of 2.91 g/cm³, fineness of 4,464 cm²/g and made of domestic G company. The chemical properties are as shown in table 4.

Table 4. The Chemistry of Blast Furnace Slag

Chemical component (%)						
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	TiO ₂
35.80	13.87	0.52	41.10	3.60	2.36	1.20

2.4.2 Red Mud

Red mud used in this study consists of Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃, and SiO₂, and because there are a lot of Fe₂O₃ component, it shows reddish color so it is called as red mud. Density of red mud is 3.37g/cm³, fineness is 3,483 cm²/g and made of domestic K company. The chemical properties are as shown in table 5.

Table 5. The Chemistry of Red Mud

Chemical component (%)						
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O
12.0	25.14	33.3	2.50	0.20	0.30	8.80

2.4.3 Silica Fume

Silica fume used in this experiment has density of 2.30 g/cm³, fineness of 220,000 cm²/g and made of foreign C company. The chemical properties are as shown in table 6.

Table 6. The Chemistry of Silica Fume

Chemical component (%)						
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	TiO ₂
94.0	2.60	1.69	0.31	1.03	0.15	-

3 Experimental results and analysis

3.1 Compressive strength by changing the CaO contents

Fig.2 the results in which compressive strength were measured by the change in CaO contents of inorganic composites. As CaO increased in contents, compressive strength increased in all ages.

Fig. 2 Compressive strength by changing the CaO contents

It seems that as the CaO contents increase, hydration is triggered, affecting the early expression of strength, causing this phenomenon. In the case that the contents of CaO are more than 30%, high intensity of more than 30 MPa on 28th day was feasible.

3.2 Compressive strength by changing the Si/Al

Fig.3 the results in which compressive strength were measured by changes the Si/Al of the inorganic composites. After 28 days of curing, Si/Al 4 displayed the highest compressive strength. After 28 days the compressive strength appeared to be appeared to be stable. Meanwhile, by day 7, Si/Al 6 showed the highest compressive strength. As Si/Al increased, SiO₂ contents increased. When CaO contents were fixed at 30%, so the early appearance of strength was good. Long-term strength was the most stable in the case of Si/Al 4, which was the best one. It seems that the results like these were produced because the ratio of inorganic composites is the most ideal when it is Si/Al 4.

Fig. 3 Compressive strength by changing the Si/Al

4 Conclusions

This study, to develop inorganic composite experiments that don't use cement, but use blast furnace slag, red-mud, and silica fume which are industrial by-products as cement substitutes. The results of the study can be summarized as follow.

1) As a result of the compressive strength test, by changing the CaO contents after fixing Si/Al to 4, while the CaO contents increased the compressive strength increased along. When the CaO contents were 35%, the compressive strength was the best.

2) As a result of the compressive strength test by changing Si/Al, after fixing the CaO contents at 30%, the compressive strength of low-carbon eco-friendly inorganic composites didn't affect Si/Al that much. According to the Si/Al, the properties of appearance in compressive strength, by each age, showed disparities in a kind.

Through the results drawn by this study, it could be found that the contents of CaO influenced the strength properties more than Si/Al. The study of how to draw the optimal mixture of low-carbon eco-friendly inorganic binder, and how to control the quantity and ratio of alkali accelerator which combine NaOH and Na₂SiO₃, is to be continued in the future.

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